

**A STUDY OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTIONS
AND ATTITUDE TOWARD TEACHING OF TEACHERS OF
TEACHER TRAINING INSTITUTES**

Shobha V. Kalebag

Mahavir College, Kolhapur

Every individual has to shoulder the responsibilities of the family. Now a days women are also sharing the responsibility of running the house. They have to perform the dual role in running the house. The working women whether she is married or unmarried, faces higher stress levels. This stress is not only at a work place but it also at home. Sometimes she has to play different roles in housework. The stress may be due to excess work, economical problems, etc. and this leads to the high stress and it reduces the job satisfaction. Many studies have shown that women have more stress than male. Counterparts especially if they have children at home.

Teacher is builder, founder and sculpture of nation. "Destiny of nation is being shaped in the classrooms." Humayun Kabir says that, "Without good teachers even the best of system is bound to fail with good teachers, even the defects of a system can be largely overcome." "Fate of society depends on the quality of its teachers. If is no exaggeration to say that incompetent and dissatisfied teachers undermine the very foundation of society."

Teachers are arguably the most important group of professionals for our nation's future. Teachers are a crucial element of educational opportunity structures. A teachers who is happy with his job, plays a pivotal role in the upliftment of society. Job is the paid position of regular employment, well-adjusted and satisfied teacher can contribute a lot to the wellbeing of his/her pupils. A dissatisfied teacher can become irritable and may create tensions which can have negative influence on the students' learning process and it

consequently affects their academic growth, job satisfaction implies the overall adjustment to work situation. Therefore it is disturbing to find that many of today's teachers are dissatisfied with their jobs.

Attitude is readiness to react towards or against some situation, person or thing in a particular manner. The attitudes, ideas, feelings and interest of students are influenced by the organization of his/her family, thinking of parents and society. Teachers having favourable attitude towards their profession and generally successful, properly adjusted and well satisfied with their job.

Objectives:

1. To study the job satisfaction of the teachers of teacher training colleges.
2. To study the attitude toward teaching of the teachers of teacher training college.
3. To find out the relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching of teachers of teacher training colleges.

Hypothesis:

For the present study the following hypothesis had been formulated.

There is no significant different between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching.

Methodology:

The following procedure was adopted for the present study.

Sample:

The study was conducted on a sample of 200 teachers of teacher training institutes of Belgaum district in Karnataka state. Purposive sampling method was used to collect the sample.

Tools used for Data Collection:

- i) Job Satisfaction Scale (TSS) by Amar Singh and T.R. Sharma.
- ii) Teacher Attitude Inventory by S.P. Ahluwalia was used to find the attitude of teachers.

Statistical Techniques Used:

Mean, standard deviation and chi-square (χ^2) were used to find the relation between job satisfaction and attitude toward teaching of teachers of teacher training institutes.

Result and Discussion:

Data Analysis:

Testing of Hypothesis:

Objective No. 1:

To find the job satisfaction of the teachers of teacher training institutes.

The table 1 shows the levels of job satisfaction of the teachers.

Table No. 1

Sr. No.	Levels of job satisfaction	No. of teachers	Percentage
1.	Extremely satisfied	115	57.50
2.	Very satisfied	54	27.00
3.	Moderately satisfied	16	8.00
4.	Not satisfied	08	4.00
5.	Extremely dissatisfied	07	3.50

Table shows the levels of job satisfaction. Out of 200 teachers 115 teachers i.e. (57.5%) are extremely satisfied, 54 teachers i.e. (27%) teachers are very satisfied, 16 teachers (8%) are moderately satisfied and 8 teachers i.e. (4%) teachers are not satisfied in their work and 7 teachers (3.5%) are extremely dissatisfied in their work.

From above it is clear that the no of extremely satisfied teachers is more.

To study attitude towards teaching

Table No. 2**Classification by using different factors as gender and rural and urban area**

		N	Mean	S.D.	Median
Male	Rural	64	240.0313	26.79004	247
	Urban	54	224.888	35.9511	225
	Total	118	233.1017	31.95131	241
Female	Rural	42	248.315	32.60545	253
	Urban	4	243.000	43.4308	253
	Total	82	245.72	33.96293	253
Total		200	237.963	33.1444	245.5

From the above table it is clear that, male from urban area are have favourable attitude towards teaching.

To find out the relation between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching

Table No. 3

There is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching of teachers of teacher training institutes.

By using two way contingency table we have co-relation between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching of the teachers.

Size of sample	Degrees of freedom	Of values of level calculated χ^2	Table values 0.05 level	Prob. Syn.
200	1	7.144	3.8414	0.008

From the above table no. 3, it is clear that the calculated χ^2 values was found to be 7.144 and table χ^2 values was 3.8414 at 0.05 level of significance which is less than the calculated χ^2 values. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is significant relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching of the teachers.

Results and Discussion:

There is significant relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching.

From the above investigation investigator conclude that the relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching is positive. It can thus be concluded that teachers who are satisfied with their job have good attitude towards their teaching.

Conclusion:

Maximum teachers of teachers' training institutes have satisfaction in their job and their attitude towards teaching is positive and good.

There is relationship between job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching is positive.

References:

- Best J. W. and Kahn, J. V. (2002), Research in Education, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
- Best, J.W. (1982), Research in Education, 4th ed. New Delhi : Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.
- Buch M. B. (1996), Fifth Survey of Research in Education, New Delhi: NCERT.
- Dash, B.N. (2005), Teacher and Education in the Emerging Indian Society (Vol. I) Hyderabad: Neelkamal Publication.
- Garret, H.E. (1967), Statistics in Psychology and Education, 4th ed. Bombay: Vakils Fetter and Simons Pvt. Ltd.
- Kothari, C.R. (2001): Research Methodology, New Delhi: Wisawa Prakashan.
- Mangal, S.K. (2004), Advanced Educational Psychology, New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.